

Comparing the roles of the sensory modalities in user-product interactions

Hendrik N.J. Schifferstein, Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology - The Netherlands

Abstract

All senses are open to receive information during user-product interactions. The present paper compares the roles the different sensory modalities play in product perception and experience. In the first study we determined how people experienced products when one of their modalities was blocked. Blocking vision resulted in the largest loss of functional information, increased task difficulty and task duration. On the other hand, product experiences increased in perceived intensity. When touch was blocked, the perceived loss of information was somewhat smaller than for vision, but now familiar products felt less as the users' own. Blocking audition or olfaction had few consequences for the functional user-product interaction, but blocking audition resulted in communication problems and blocking olfaction decreased experience intensity.

We also studied the roles of the modalities simultaneously in a complete product by manipulating several sensory product aspects. We first selected a product evaluation dimension equally relevant for all modalities: pleasantness. Subsequently, we developed a concept for a new product: a portable air purifier. We determined the pleasantness of several product appearances, sounds, feels, and smells, and we selected stimulus pairs (one for each modality) that differed to similar degrees. These stimuli were combined to yield 16 different products. However, no differences were found in the pleasantness ratings of these product prototypes in a consumer test. Possibly, our stimulus manipulations were too subtle to affect product evaluations. Although the outcomes did not allow us to estimate the relative importances of the various modalities, the proposed approach with more extreme stimulus manipulations seems promising for future studies.

For designers it is important to pay attention to how their products impact on the various senses. The outcomes of this research can help designers to select the optimal sensory channel to communicate a certain message, to select the most efficient channel to improve a product, or to make designers aware of the sensory complexity of the product experience.

Key words: senses

Introduction

During the interaction with a product, all the user's senses are open to receive information. Each modality is sensitive to a different type of stimulation and, consequently, not all the incoming sensory information necessarily communicates the same message. Some sensations trigger feelings and emotions, some evoke memories or associations to other objects. Product experiences depend on all the incoming sensory messages, whether perceived consciously or not, and on the interpretation of these messages. The present paper compares the roles the different sensory modalities play in product perception and experience.

Popular belief holds that vision dominates human experience. When people are asked which sensory modality they would miss most if they lost it, the majority are likely to indicate vision. In an evaluation of the roles of the sensory modalities in user-product interactions, however, people reported that they found one of the other sensory modalities more important than vision for about half of the products tested (Schifferstein, 2006). For example, for a computer mouse the tactual characteristics were reported to be most important, for a vacuum cleaner the sound it made, for a cleaning product its smell, and for a soft drink its taste. The relative importance of a modality may depend on various aspects, such as the types of sensory stimulation and their variability over products, the relevance of the sensory information for functional usage, and its role in enjoying the product. For some products the usage experience depends mainly on one modality (e.g., vase), whereas for other products four or more modalities are important (e.g., car, vacuum cleaner, shoes, cookies) (Schifferstein, 2006).

Processing visual information is very different from processing olfactory information. Hinton and Henley (1993) asked participants to write down whatever came to their minds when they perceived either a smell or a picture of a product. Responses cued by olfaction consisted of fewer words, were more personal, and had stronger affective components than responses cued by visual stimuli. Adjectives used to describe the smell usually referred to the smell experience itself (e.g., citrus, sweet, and sour for an orange), whereas the visual stimulus elicited remarks about texture, shape, and color and evoked more cognitive associations (e.g., Florida, vitamin C, healthy).

The affective dimension seems to dominate olfactory cognition. Odor pleasantness plays an important role in odor categorizations and smell experiences are largely idiosyncratic

(Dubois, 2000). In addition, emotions play an important role in the memories elicited by odors (Herz and Schooler, 2002). Visual input, on the other hand, seems to be linked most directly to stored knowledge, such as information on production method, region of origin, and product safety (Hinton and Henley, 1993).

Audition and touch seem to lie somewhere in between these two extremes. Because audition is involved in speech perception just as vision is, it is likely to be closely associated to logical reasoning and established knowledge. However, audition is also involved in music perception, which has a large emotional component (Herz, 1998). For touch, the good identification performance for common objects (95-96%) (Klatzky et al., 1985) is likely to promote its usefulness for the functional usage of products. In addition, it is likely to possess a substantial emotional component, because touch also plays an important role in interpersonal intimacy (Fischer et al., 1976).

To assess the potential contribution of each sensory modality to the product experience, Schifferstein and Cleiren (2005) presented participants with multisensory products through a single sensory modality (vision, touch, audition, or olfaction) and asked them to describe their experience. They found that vision and touch provided the largest number of details about a product. The product sound was less informative, while the product smell provided the least information. The relatively large number of details obtained with vision and touch made product identification easiest and yielded the clearest associations to events, people, and other products. Because vision gathers information about many product aspects more rapidly than touch (Jones and O'Neil, 1985), vision is likely to dominate product experiences in real-life situations. Also, vision can be used to explore large objects in a minimum of time, whereas this would be impossible for touch. As a consequence, vision has been found to guide object exploration through other modalities (Heller, 1982).

Blocking the senses

To compare the impact of the various modalities on product experiences in daily life, we conducted a study in which we investigated the effect of blocking single modalities during user-product interactions (Schifferstein and Desmet, 2006). Twenty people participated in one out of four experimental conditions in which one sensory modality (vision, audition, touch, or

olfaction) was blocked, or in a control condition in which participants could employ all their sensory modalities. In all conditions the participants actively explored and used the product.

Vision was blocked by wearing ski goggles covered with black tape, audition was blocked by presenting white noise through a headphone, tactual perception was blocked by wearing thick, inflexible oven gloves, and olfaction was blocked with an adjustable nose clip. Responses were recorded either in writing or verbally.

Eight tasks were chosen to represent a number of common daily activities with products in which multiple sensory modalities were involved. For healthy individuals, these tasks were easy to perform: squeezing an orange, boiling water in an electric water boiler, cleaning a table with a spray cleaner, eating a chocolate cookie, brushing their teeth, vacuum cleaning a carpet, taking off and putting on one of their shoes, and composing an SMS message on their mobile phone. After performing each task, a printed questionnaire was filled out.

Table 1. Mean responses in the various conditions during the eight experimental tasks
(adapted from Schifferstein & Desmet, 2006)

	Control	Blocked modality			
		Vision	Hearing	Touch	Smell
All products					
Proportion of task performed independently (0-100%)	100.0 ^b	93.3 ^a	99.8 ^b	97.1 ^b	98.9 ^b
Difficulty of performing this task (1-7)	1.1 ^b	2.7 ^a	1.2 ^b	2.6 ^a	1.1 ^b
Estimated relative task duration (%)		202 ^a	104 ^b	219 ^a	100 ^b
Six unknown products					
Number of aspects simultaneously (1-7)	5.0 ^b	3.1 ^a	4.5 ^b	4.6 ^b	4.7 ^b
Proportion of information missed (0-100%)		40 ^a	27 ^b	27 ^b	21 ^b
Two familiar products					
Experience as different (1-7)	1.4 ^b	2.9 ^a	1.7 ^b	4.0 ^c	1.1 ^b
Experience as own (1-7)	6.8 ^b	5.8 ^{ac}	6.6 ^{ab}	5.0 ^c	6.8 ^b

^{abc} Means with the same superscripts did not differ significantly in a post hoc test with Bonferroni adjustment [$p > 0.05$]

For all products we obtained measures that indicated how difficult it was to perform the task independently (Table 1). These measures generally indicated that visual and tactual impairments made the tasks harder to perform: The difficulty of performing the given task increased and the estimated duration of the task doubled. In addition, participants reported that they could no longer perform the entire task independently. With an auditory or olfactory impairment, task difficulty was similar to the control condition.

For the six tasks involving unknown products, the visual impairment decreased the amount of product information more than the other impairments: The proportion of information missed was larger and the number of product details perceived simultaneously was judged to be smaller. Participants experienced the two familiar products as different from usual and less as

their own when the visual or tactual senses were blocked. Note that the latter is the only effect that is larger for touch than for vision.

After performing the tasks, participants reported how they had experienced the products during the eight tasks compared to usual. For all modalities, introducing an impairment made products less predictable and more difficult to verify. In addition, blocking visual perception made experiences more intense, although they also became less pleasant. Ratings for audition suggest a decrease mainly for provoking and stimulating. For touch the decrease is mainly found for pleasantness and feeling good. For smell, the effect of the impairment seems most dramatic, with convincing decreases for all items.

Table 2. Mean responses for how a product was experienced compared to usual (scale from -3 to +3; ** p<0.01 and * p<0.05; Schifferstein & Desmet, 2006)

	Blocked modality			
	Vision	Hearing	Touch	Smell
Pleasant	-1.00 **	-0.50 *	-1.65 **	-1.10 **
Good	-0.05	-0.35	-0.80 **	-1.85 **
Provoking	-0.20	-1.00 **	-0.80 *	-1.10 **
Stimulating	-0.55	-0.75 **	-0.55	-0.80 **
Intense	+0.85 **	-0.50	-0.30	-1.05 **
Emotional	+0.40	-0.50 *	-0.10	-1.05 **
Predictable	-1.80 **	-0.90 **	-1.45 **	-0.55 *
Verifiable	-2.00 **	-1.25 **	-2.40 **	-0.55 **

Participants also indicated to what extent they agreed with a number of statements regarding their experience with the impairment (Table 3). Participants with a visual impairment were sometimes afraid to move, probably because they were afraid to get hurt or to damage things. On the positive side, it seems that the visual impairment gave the opportunity to think better and to pay attention to other product aspects. The auditorily impaired more often felt cut off from the outside world. In all experimental manipulations, participants tended to agree with the statement that they used their other senses more due to the blocking of one modality.

However, this effect was smaller for olfaction than for the other three. Blocking the nose resulted in a decrease of appetite for food.

Table 3. Mean ratings of agreement with post-task ratings
(4-point scale; adapted from Schifferstein & Desmet, 2006).

	Blocked modality			
	Vision	Hearing	Touch	Smell
I did not dare to move	2.50 ^a	1.75 ^b	1.00 ^c	1.25 ^{bc}
I was afraid that I would hurt myself	2.10 ^a	1.35 ^b	1.32 ^b	1.20 ^b
I was afraid that I would damage things	2.05 ^a	1.80 ^{ab}	1.84 ^{ab}	1.25 ^b
I could think well	3.25 ^a	2.80 ^{ab}	2.47 ^b	2.20 ^b
I felt cut off from the outside world	2.55 ^{ac}	3.20 ^a	1.90 ^{bc}	1.70 ^b
I had trouble concentrating	1.60 ^{ab}	2.05 ^a	1.32 ^b	1.65 ^{ab}
I used my other senses more	3.75 ^a	3.25 ^a	3.11 ^a	2.65 ^b
My appetite decreased	2.15 ^{ac}	1.75 ^{bc}	1.21 ^b	2.80 ^a

^{abc} Means with the same superscripts did not differ significantly in a post hoc test with Bonferroni adjustment [$p > 0.05$]

In conclusion, this study suggests that blocking vision increased task difficulty and task duration, and fostered dependency on other people. On the other hand, the other senses were used more and product experiences increased in perceived intenseness. When touch was blocked, the perceived loss of information was somewhat smaller than for vision, but familiar products felt less as the users' own. Blocking audition or olfaction had few consequences for the functional user-product interaction. However, blocking audition resulted in communication problems and feeling cut off from the world. Blocking olfaction mainly decreased the intenseness of the experience: how good the product felt, and how stimulating it was. These outcomes suggest that vision mainly plays a functional role in everyday user-product interactions, whereas the main role for olfaction lies in the affective domain.

Studying all senses simultaneously in an integrated product

When people report how important they find the various modalities during the interaction with a product, considerable differences are found between product categories (Schifferstein, 2006). However, introspective self-reports can only reflect what people are aware of. They do not necessarily reflect the impact the different senses have on the overall product experience. Especially for the 'lower' senses, which are almost never in the centre of attention, their importance may be underestimated. Therefore, we developed a stepwise, experimental approach to determine the importance of the different senses in a complete product (Schifferstein et al., 2006). We created conditions under which the inputs for all modalities could be manipulated independently, in order to assess the effects of these stimulus changes on the product evaluation. We use the term 'product' to refer to a source of multimodal stimulation, whereas we use 'stimulus' for a product aspect that stimulates a single modality.

To determine the importance of the sensory modalities in the interaction with products, one needs to ensure that the experimental design does not favor one sensory modality over the others. Therefore, we first selected a product evaluation dimension that was equally relevant for all sensory modalities. For 59 semantic items we asked participants to answer the question 'Suppose that you would have to rate a product on the following semantic scale, to what extent would the sensory modalities play a role?' on a 5-point scale, ranging from 'not at all' on the left side to 'very large extent' on the right side. For each item, the degree of sensory relevance was rated for olfaction, touch, audition, and vision. A substantial part of the semantic items were obtained from questionnaires using the Semantic Differential Method (Osgood et al., 1957), that typically yields a semantic space defined by three orthogonal dimensions in factor analysis: Evaluation, Activity, and Potency. Part of our results is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Mean relevance ratings of four sensory modalities for the evaluation of various semantic attributes (7-point scale) (adapted from Schifferstein et al., 2006).

	Modality			
	Vision	Audition	Touch	Smell
Evaluative				
Beautiful – ugly	5.0	3.7	2.9	2.2
Pleasant – unpleasant	4.5	4.3	4.5	4.5
Agreeable – disagreeable	3.8	3.9	3.9	3.9
Good – bad	3.6	3.4	3.2	2.8
Attractive – unattractive	4.7	3.7	3.9	4.0
Activity				
Stimulating – relaxing	3.4	3.8	3.5	2.9
Excited – calm	4.1	4.3	3.4	2.6
Fast – slow	4.2	3.6	2.8	1.5
Fussy – lethargic	4.5	3.8	2.1	1.4
Lively – quiet	4.5	4.5	3.1	2.5
Potency				
Cute – tough	4.8	3.7	3.2	2.2
Masculine – feminine	4.5	3.7	3.8	3.5
Strong – weak	3.7	3.0	3.9	2.3
Momentous – humble	4.3	3.3	2.6	1.7
Persistent – accommodating	3.6	3.2	2.9	1.7
Other				
Rough – soft	4.2	3.0	5.0	2.0
Fresh – musty	3.4	1.9	2.6	5.0
Loud – quiet	2.3	4.9	2.2	1.3
Funny – serious	4.0	4.0	2.2	1.6
Safe – dangerous	4.3	3.9	3.5	3.2
Valuable – worthless	4.6	3.6	3.8	2.6
Modern – traditional	4.7	3.4	2.9	2.8

Only four semantic scales did not show a significant difference between the modalities: agreeable-disagreeable ($p=0.83$), pleasant-unpleasant ($p=0.55$), stimulating-relaxing ($p=0.05$), and good-bad ($p=0.05$). In accordance with reports from a similar study performed in Japan (Gyoba et al., 2005), most of the items that are sensory neutral contribute to the Evaluation factor. Therefore, we used the pleasantness of the product as the dimension on which we evaluated the impact of the four sensory modalities. This dimension is assessed by averaging the responses on the three items agreeable-disagreeable, pleasant-unpleasant, and good-bad.

Subsequently, we developed a concept for a new product: a portable air purifier. This is a small object that people can take with them as an accessory. It is used to provide fresh air by filtering the polluted air that surrounds them. For this product, we designed 7 different appearances (color, air hole pattern), 11 sounds (fan sounds), 9 different feels (weight and weight distribution), and 10 fragrances that could be varied independently, without stimulating other modalities. The pleasantness of all these stimuli for use in the portable air purifier was determined in another pre-study. To make sure that our manipulations were equivalent, we chose the pair with the smallest difference in scores for each modality from the sets of stimulus pairs that yielded a significant difference in pleasantness scores [$p<0.0025$]. This assured that the stimulus pairs differed approximately to the same extent in pleasantness when evaluated in isolation.

These stimuli were combined using a full factorial 2^4 design to yield 16 different products, varying from a product composed of all pleasant stimuli to a product composed of all unpleasant stimuli. 322 naïve consumers evaluated one of the 16 air purifiers, resulting in 20 or more observations per prototype. However, no significant effects were found in the pleasantness evaluations of these different product prototypes. We suspect that our stimulus manipulations were possibly too subtle to have a convincing effect on product evaluations.

One reason why the differences between the prototypes were small is because the freedom of designing stimuli was restricted. On the one hand, the experimental demand to use only stimuli that could be manipulated independently of one another made it impossible to use stimulus dimensions such as size, shape, and surface texture, because they can be perceived by both touch and vision. Furthermore, loud sounds could not be used, because their vibrations can be perceived tactually. On the other hand, choosing a portable air purifier as the test product limited variation in product size and weight. Moreover, because we wanted to

develop a plausible and realistic product concept that could be introduced on the market, we were limited in the sounds the product was likely to make and the types of smells it would disperse. As a consequence, the additional demand to make the pleasantness differences comparable in size for all modalities severely restricted manipulations.

Another aspect that deserves attention is the involvement of product designers in our research approach. We used designers' input, because we wanted to derive knowledge that is not only theoretically interesting, but also applicable in the design practice. However, the way in which designers tend to adapt a product concept at the end of the design process may be quite subtle and may not be radical enough to affect consumer evaluations. Designers probably consider large differences in stimulus properties as obvious, extreme, over-the-top manipulations. Nevertheless, the latter differences are likely to result in statistically significant effects and, therefore, tend to be used in experimental research.

Although the outcomes did not allow us to estimate the relative importances of the various modalities for the user-product interaction with the portable air purifier, the proposed approach with more extreme stimulus manipulations seems an interesting addition to the methods currently employed in sensory dominance research. We plan to use such an approach in future studies.

Design implications

For designers it is important to pay attention to how their products impact on the various senses. The research approach presented above can serve to answer several questions that can come up during the design process, such as:

- To communicate the product identity and the product benefits, the designer may employ different sensory channels. Each channel has its own strengths and weaknesses. A designer, who is aware of these, will be better in transmitting this message. Our data suggest that functional information can best be communicated through vision, whereas for affective information the other modalities may be more suitable (Table 2).
- A designer who knows how important a sensory modality is for the product may decide to put the majority of the design effort in pleasing the most important modality, because this seems most cost efficient. He or she may also decide to focus on the modalities that were neglected thus far, to create innovative, refreshing product concepts.

- When multiple senses play an important role in the interaction with the product, the designer should pay attention to all these senses. If one aspect is neglected, it is likely to deteriorate product performance and market success considerably.

Designers are likely to benefit from further research in this area.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by MAGW VIDI grant 452-02-028 of the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (N.W.O.). The author would like to thank Eliane Scharten and Samantha Hosea for their contribution to data collection.

References

- Dubois, D. (2000) "Categories as acts of meaning: the case of categories in olfaction and audition." *Cognitive Science Quarterly* 1: 35-68.
- Fischer, J. D., Rytting, M. and Heslin, R. (1976) "Hands touching hands: affective and evaluative effects of interpersonal touch." *Sociometry* 39: 416-421.
- Gyoba, J., Suzuki, M., Kawabata, H., Yamaguchi, H. and Komatsu, H. (2005) *Analyses of sensory-relevance of adjective pairs frequently used in the semantic differential method*. 6th Annual Meeting of the International Multisensory Research Forum, Rovereto, Italy.
- Heller, M. A. (1982) "Visual and tactual texture perception: intersensory cooperation." *Perception & Psychophysics* 31: 339-344.
- Herz, R. S. (1998) "Are odors the best cues to memory? A cross-modal comparison of associative memory stimuli." *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 855: 670-674.
- Herz, R. S. and Schooler, J. W. (2002) "A naturalistic study of autobiographical memories evoked by olfactory and visual cues: testing the Proustian hypothesis." *American Journal of Psychology* 115: 21-32.
- Hinton, P. B. and Henley, T. B. (1993) "Cognitive and affective components of stimuli presented in three modes." *Bulletin of the Psychonomic Society* 31: 595-598.
- Jones, B. and O'Neil, S. (1985) "Combining vision and touch in texture perception." *Perception & Psychophysics* 37: 66-72.
- Klatzky, R. L., Lederman, S. J. and Metzger, V. A. (1985) "Identifying objects by touch: an "expert system"." *Perception & Psychophysics* 37: 299-302.
- Osgood, C. E., Suci, G. J. and Tannenbaum, P. H. (1957) *The Measurement of Meaning*. Urbana, IL: University of Illinois Press.
- Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2006) "The relative importance of sensory modalities in product usage: a study of self-reports." *Acta Psychologica* 121: 41-64.
- Schifferstein, H. N. J. and Cleiren, M. P. H. D. (2005) "Capturing product experiences: a split-modality approach." *Acta Psychologica* 118: 293-318.
- Schifferstein, H. N. J. and Desmet, P. M. A. (2006) "The effect of sensory impairments on product experience and personal well-being." submitted.
- Schifferstein, H. N. J., Otten, J. J. and Hekkert, P. (2006) "An experimental approach to assess sensory dominance in a product development context." submitted.

